

Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* artemisinin-based combination therapy gene mutation in chukwuodumegwu ojukwu university teaching hospital Awka

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Abstract

Background: Monitoring *Plasmodium falciparum* Kelch 13 (*pfk13*) gene mutations linked to artemisinin resistance is critical for understanding the spread of drug-resistant malaria. Although *pfk13* mutations have been observed in various regions of Nigeria, limited molecular epidemiological studies on field *P. falciparum* isolates have been conducted.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence of *pfk13* gene mutations associated with artemisinin resistance in *P. falciparum* isolates from malaria patients at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu Teaching Hospital (COOUTH), Anambra State, Nigeria.

Method: A total of 186 participants were included, consisting of 98 females (52.7%) and 88 males (47.3%), with 51.1% in the 18-30 age group. Most participants had secondary (43.0%) or tertiary (35.5%) education. The largest occupational group was students (40.3%). Blood samples were collected from patients diagnosed with malaria using rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) and microscopy. The *pfk13* gene was amplified via nested polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and sequenced with ABI 3031 sanger sequencer to detect polymorphisms.

Result: The study revealed five distinct *pfk13* mutant alleles: G548G, A577S, P615P, A626A, and V638D. Two non-synonymous mutations (A577S and V638D) occurred at positions 1732 and 1908, while three synonymous mutations (G548G, A577S, and A626A) were detected at different positions. None of the mutations associated with delayed parasite clearance or artemisinin resistance, such as C580Y, R539T, Y493H, or M476I, were found in the analyzed samples.

Conclusion: This study identified new *pfk13* gene polymorphisms in *P. falciparum* isolates from Anambra State. Although no mutations linked to artemisinin resistance were found, the detection of non-synonymous mutations emphasizes the importance of ongoing genomic surveillance to monitor resistance patterns and safeguard the efficacy of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) in malaria control.

Keywords: *Plasmodium falciparum*; *pfk13* gene; Artemisinin resistance; Molecular epidemiology; Malaria

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1. Introduction

Malaria is a major cause of death and illness in many developing countries, where young people and pregnant women are particularly vulnerable. According to the World Health Organization's 2023 Malaria Report, almost half of the world's population lives in areas at risk of malaria transmission in 87 countries and territories [15]. The overall mortality rate was 15.1 per 100,000 people and the annual malaria-specific mortality rate was 2.4 per 100,000 people [9]. Overall mortality reached its peak in 1998 at 23.6 per 100,000 people and then decreased to 9.6 per 100,000 people in 2004 [6]. Malaria-specific mortality followed a similar trend but had two peaks: in 1995 at 3.6 per 100,000 people and in 2002 at 2.9 per 100,000 people [6].

The World Health Organization has set an ambitious goal of reducing morbidity and mortality from malaria by 90%. This is especially important for *Plasmodium falciparum* (*P. falciparum*), the species most likely to cause malaria and death [15]. Artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT) has been effective as a first-line treatment for malaria in all age groups. However, when used alone, artemether has not been able to fully clear all asexual and sexual stage parasitemia [3]. This is why combination chemotherapy is recommended for the treatment of malaria. The use of these therapies has also reduced the incidence of drug resistance due to their additive and synergistic effects.

Malaria remains a serious public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa in spite of the reduction in morbidity and mortality observed in recent years [12]. The control of malaria is partly related to the use of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) in almost all endemic countries in combination with other strategies. The WHO recommends that the efficacy of the first line and second-line anti-malarial drugs should be consistently assessed for early detection and prevention of the spread of resistant parasite populations [1]. With malaria being one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality especially in tropical countries, a further rise of an already high burden of malaria is a cause for concern [11]. Artemisinin is a sesquiterpene lactone which contains the peroxide group. Artemisinin is extracted and isolated from the leaves of *Artemisia annua*. The drug and its derivatives have a role in eliminating *Plasmodium falciparum* by inhibiting the activity of phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase (*PfPI3K*) [4]. Artemisinin based combination therapy contains one of three artemisinin derivatives: artesunate, artemether or dihydroartemisinin (DHA). Oral artesunate and artemether are active but are also converted by blood esterases and hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes respectively to DHA, which provides the majority of their activity [14]. In Africa, ACT is the first-line anti-malarial treatment and remains efficacious and safe. However, resistance to previous generations of anti-malarial drugs such as chloroquine, sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) emerged in the 1970s in Southeast Asia and finally spread to the Indian sub-continent and then to Africa. It is, therefore, important that continuous monitoring of the therapeutic response of ACT is carried out in endemic areas in order to detect early warning signs and effectively track which contain the development and spread of artemisinin resistance [10].

The crucial breakthrough came at the end of 2013 when parasites cultured for five years under intermittent artemisinin pressure were sequenced [10] and a mutation found close to the chromosome 13 region identified in the genetic association studies [10]. The mutated gene in question encodes a protein containing a 'kelch' motif [2] and is now generally known as 'K13'. A high proportion of Cambodian isolates had mutations in K13's 'propeller' region, a six-bladed structure that mediates interactions between kelch proteins and other macromolecules [14]. K13 mutations are also found in Africa, but only at very low prevalence (and the mutations associated with ACT resistance in Asia are virtually absent). There is currently no detectable impact of K13 mutations on ACT efficacy in Africa, except for one recent report of a migrant worker with a *P. falciparum* K13-variant infection from western Africa who showed delayed parasite clearance following ACT treatment. Explanations for the current lack of impact of K13 mutations in Africa could include the greater degree of acquired immunity there, resulting from repeated exposure to *P. falciparum*, which builds host immunity to help control drug-resistant infections [13].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

syringe, latex glove, micropipette, centrifuge, ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA) tubes, Rapid diagnostic test (RDT), primers, Agorose 2% gel, PCR, sequencer, ethidium bromide, Qiagen DNA mini extraction kit (Qiagen, Germany).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Study location

The study was conducted at COOUTH, Awka, Anambra state. Anambra is a state in southeastern Nigeria. The capital and seat of government is Awka. The state has a projected population of 5.8 million in 2017. The state is the 2nd most densely populated state in Nigeria after Lagos state in the south west with a total land area of 4,844 km² and a population density of 860 km². Awka is in the tropical rainforest zone of Nigeria and experiences two distinct seasons brought about by the two predominant winds that rule the area. The temperature in Awka is generally 27-30 degrees Celsius between June and December but rises to 32-34 degrees between January and April. Awka lies below 300 meters above sea in a valley on the plains of Mamu River.

2.2.2. Sample size

Using an estimated population size of malaria diagnosed patients in COOUTH and the rate of prevalence of malaria in the state (75%), the sample size was calculated with a 95% confident interval and precision level of 5% as follows:

$$n_o = Z^2pq/e^2$$

where:

n = sample size

z = 1.96 at 95%

p = Prevalence rate

e = sampling error that can be tolerated (0.05)

$$q = 1-p \text{ (Cochran, 1977)}$$

$$n = 1.96^2 \times 0.75 \times 0.25 / (0.05)^2$$

$$n = 183$$

2.2.3. Ethical approval

The study protocol was approved by the Ethics committee Board of the COOUTH (COOUTH/CMAC/ETH.C/VOL.1/04/0002). Informed consent was obtained from all study participants and/or their guardians before sample collection.

2.2.4. Study population

The participants are both male and female with obvious symptoms of malaria. Both male and female individuals aged between 18 to 60 years and above who are confirmed malaria positive patients. Exclusion was based on refusal of consent to participate in the study and falling outside the age (18-60 years).

2.2.5. Sample Collection

Blood samples were collected through venepuncture into EDTA tubes from patients diagnosed with malaria. Plasmodial infection was diagnosed using RDT and microscopy. The blood sample was stored at -80°C.

2.2.6. DNA Extraction

The blood samples were stored at -20°C and Genomic DNA was extracted using Quick-DNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo Research) and procedure in order to purify the RBC fractions and release the DNA. 200 µl of each blood sample was added to a microcentrifuge tube. 200 µl of BioFluid & Cell Buffer and 20 µl of Proteinase K were added to it and mixed thoroughly using a vortex for 10-15 seconds and then incubated the tube at 55°C for 10 minutes on a heating block. 1 volume Genomic Binding Buffer (i.e. 420 µl) was added to the digested sample and mixed thoroughly with a vortex mixer for 10-15 seconds. The mixture was then transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IIC-XL Column in a Collection Tube and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube was discarded with the flow through. 400 µl DNA Pre-Wash Buffer was added to the spin column in a new Collection Tube and centrifuged at 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The collection tube was emptied and 700 µl g-DNA Wash Buffer was added to the spin column and centrifuged at ≥ 12,000 x g for 1 minute. The spin column was then transferred to a clean microcentrifuge tube. 50 µl of DNA Elution Buffer was added directly on the matrix and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature, then centrifuged at maximum speed for 1 minute to elute the DNA. The eluted DNA was stored ≤ -20°C for future use.

2.2.7. *Pfk13* Gene Genotyping

The detection of the *Pfk13* mutations was done using nested PCR followed by sequencing. This was done through nested PCR, a two-step amplification method that increases sensitivity and specificity for the *Pfk13* target. The primer pair was used for amplification of the target DNA sequence: Forward Primer: 5'-GGGAATCTGGTGGTAACAGC-3' and Reverse Primer: 5'-GCCTTGTTGAAAGAAGCAGA-3'. These primers were selected based on their specificity to the target region and optimized for melting temperature and minimal secondary structure formation.

For the first round PCR, a 25 µL reaction mixture was prepared containing template DNA, outer primers (0.2 µM final concentration), dNTPs (200 µM each), 1× PCR buffer with MgCl₂ (1.5–2.0 mM final concentration), and Taq DNA polymerase (1.25 U).

Thermal cycling conditions included; Initial denaturation at 94°C for 2 minutes, 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds plus annealing at 58°C for 30 seconds and extension at 72°C for 1 minute then final extension at 72°C for 5 minutes. The amplified product was used as a template for the nested PCR round.

For the Second Round (Nested) PCR, a second 25 µL reaction was set up using 1–2 µL of the first-round product and nested primers targeting an internal region of the original amplicon. The thermocycler settings followed the same profile, with minor adjustments to the annealing temperature based on the nested primers' T_m.

2.2.8. Gel Electrophoresis

PCR products from both rounds were resolved on a 2% agarose gel, suitable for separating small DNA fragments. The gel was stained with ethidium bromide and visualized under UV light. Distinct bands confirmed successful and specific amplification of the target sequence.

After PCR, ABI 3130 sequencer was performed to identify specific mutations within the gene. These genetic changes help determine whether the malaria strain might resist artemisinin therapy.

Sequences were analysed by ABI 3031 sequencer using CodonCode Aligner version 4.0 (CodonCode Corporate, USA) by assembling the reads with the *Pfk13* reference sequence (*Plasmodium falciparum* 3D7 strain). The raw chromatogram files were reviewed for quality using the software Chromas. Visually confirming base calls from chromatograms to identify single nucleotide polymorphisms.

2.2.9. Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed using GraphPad. The effect of *Pfk13* genotypes and haemoglobin values on parasite density was determined using multiple logistic regressions. Odds ratios and correlation models were applied to assess the association between parasite density and haemoglobin concentration.

This section presents the results of the study, focusing on the demographic characteristics of the participants.

3. Results

Table 1 The Demographic Information of the participants

Variables	Descriptors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	88	47.3%
	Female	98	52.7%
Age	18-30	95	51.1%
	31-50	70	37.6%
	Above 50	21	11.3%
Educational Level	No formal education	10	5.4%
	Primary	30	16.1%
	Secondary	80	43.0%

	Tertiary	66	35.5%
Occupation	Student	75	40.3%
	Healthcare worker	30	16.1%
	Civil servant	41	22.0%
	Self-employed	40	21.5%
Residence	Urban	85	45.7%
	Rural	65	34.9%
	Semi-urban	36	19.4%
Tribe	Igbo	140	75.3%
	Hausa	15	8.1%
	Yoruba	18	9.7%
	Others	13	7.0%

The demographic distribution of the 186 participants. The study included a total of 186 participants, comprising 98 females (52.7%) and 88 males (47.3%).

Table 2 Occurrence of Single Nucleotide Polymorphism

Sample Code	Wild	Mutant	Position	Codon	Amino Acid Change	Type of Mutation
FTE 448	GGC	GGT	1644	548	G548G	Synonymous Mutation
	Glycine	Glycine				
FTE493	GCT	TCT	1732	577	A577S	Non-Synonymous Mutation
	Alanine	Serine				
FTE423	CCA	CCC	1844	615	P615P	Synonymous Mutation
	Proline	Proline				
FTE 423	GCA	GCC	1877	626	A626A	Synonymous Mutation
	Alanine	Alanine				
FTE442	GTT	GAT	1908	638	V638D	Non-Synonymous Mutation
	Valine	Aspartic Acid				
Prevalence= 5%, Statistical Significance (p-value) = 0.0034						

The table presented above illustrates the mutations identified in the *Pfk13* gene from samples collected from COOUTH, Anambra State, Southeastern Nigeria, following molecular analysis. In a dataset of 100 samples, 5 exhibited SNPs, yielding a 5% prevalence.

4. Discussion

This study provides the genetic mutation of *P. falciparum* strains in Southeastern Nigeria, particularly in Anambra State. In terms of age, the 18-30 age groups constituted the largest proportion of participants at 51.1%, followed by the 31-50 age group, which represented 37.6% of the sample. The above 50 age group accounted for the smallest portion at 11.3%. Regarding educational level, the majority of participants had either secondary (43.0%) or tertiary (35.5%) education. A smaller proportion had primary education (16.1%) or no formal education (5.4%). Occupationally, students represented the largest group (40.3%), which is consistent with the study's location in a university teaching hospital. Healthcare workers (16.1%) were also well-represented. Civil servants (22.0%) and self-employed individuals (21.5%) further diversified the occupational spectrum. Finally, in terms of residence, most participants came from urban areas (45.7%), followed by rural (34.9%) and semi-urban (19.4%) areas. Tribal distribution was also noteworthy, with Igbo

participants making up the majority (75.3%), followed by smaller proportions of Hausa (8.1%) and Yoruba (9.7%), reflecting the regional demographics. The remaining 7.0% were from other ethnic groups, indicating some ethnic diversity within the study sample.

A binomial test comparing the observed prevalence to an expected 1% yielded a p-value of 0.0034, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). The study successfully revealed new polymorphisms in five of the samples. These mutations were observed at codons 548, 577, 615, 626, and 638, corresponding to nucleotide positions 1644, 1732, 1844, 1877, and 1908, respectively. Sample FTE 448 exhibited a nucleotide change from C to T at position 1644, resulting in a synonymous mutation (G548G), where the amino acid remains unchanged. Similarly, sample FTE 423 displayed a synonymous mutation at codon 615 (P615P), where the amino acid remains unchanged, and another synonymous mutation at codon 626 (A626A), where

In contrast, sample FTE 493 demonstrated a nucleotide change from G to T at position 1732, resulting in a non-synonymous mutation (A577S), where alanine is substituted by serine. Three (3) were synonymous mutations, while two (2) were non-synonymous, altering protein structure. Additionally, sample FTE 442 showed a nucleotide substitution from T to A at position 1908, leading to a non-synonymous mutation (V638D), where valine is replaced by aspartic acid.

The detection of five mutations in the *PfK13* gene, including two non-synonymous mutations, highlights the evolving nature of malaria parasites and their potential for resistance to ACTs. While no direct link has yet been established between these mutations and delayed parasite clearance or artemisinin resistance, their presence warrants further investigation. Continued surveillance of *PfK13* gene mutations in Nigeria is crucial to ensure that malaria control programs remain effective. While the current study indicates that *PfK13* mutations are still relatively rare in Nigeria, the findings highlight the importance of ongoing molecular surveillance in malaria control programs to detect and manage emerging resistance mutations before they become widespread.

The findings of this study reveal five distinct mutations in the *PfK13* gene of *Plasmodium falciparum* samples from Southeastern Nigeria, specifically Anambra State. The mutations include two non-synonymous mutations (A577S and V638D) and three synonymous mutations (G548G, A626A, and P615P). These results offer valuable insights into the molecular dynamics of malaria resistance, specifically in the context of Nigeria, a country with a high burden of malaria. This study also contributes to the ongoing efforts to monitor artemisinin resistance in the regions, particularly considering the widespread use of artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) in malaria treatment.

In the present study, the two non-synonymous mutations, A577S and V638D, were observed at positions 1732 and 1908, respectively. These mutations lead to changes in the amino acid sequence, which have no significant implications for the function of the *PfK13* protein. In contrast, the synonymous mutations (G548G, A626A, and P615P) did not result in changes to the amino acid sequence but could still influence gene expression, protein folding, or translation efficiency. These findings are consistent with previous studies on *PfK13* mutations linked to delayed parasite clearance and reduced efficacy of ACTs, as reported in Southeast Asia [7]. However, the specific mutations observed in this study were not among those previously associated with artemisinin resistance, such as C580Y, R539T, Y493H, and M476I, which are commonly found in Southeast Asia [7].

The lack of these particular mutations in the current study suggests that *Plasmodium falciparum* strains circulating in Anambra State may differ genetically from those found in Southeast Asia, where artemisinin resistance has been more prevalent. Notably, the absence of these mutations could imply that, while there is some genetic variation within the *PfK13* gene in Nigeria, the region may not yet exhibit the same level of resistance to ACTs as seen in Southeast Asia. This is consistent with reports from other regions in Africa, such as the study by Mayengue [7] in the Republic of Congo, where only a limited A578S mutation was detected. This points to the possibility that while genetic diversity exists, the extent of resistance may be localized and not yet widespread in the region.

Nigeria, having withdrawn chloroquine from malaria treatment due to resistance issues, has adopted ACTs as the first-line treatment for uncomplicated malaria [8]. The most used ACT in Nigeria is Artemether-lumefantrine, with others including dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine and amodiaquine-artesunate [8]. The widespread use of ACTs in Nigeria, particularly in regions like COOUTH, Anambra State, which serves as a referral center, could influence the emergence of new mutations. It is plausible that the mutations observed in this study are a result of selective pressure from the extensive use of ACTs, although no direct correlation between these specific mutations and ACT resistance has been established yet.

Despite the detection of new polymorphisms in this study, the findings are not entirely consistent with a previous study in Southwestern Nigeria by Ikegbunam [5] where two new polymorphisms, V581I and V520A, were identified. These variations in observed mutations could reflect geographical and temporal differences in *P. falciparum* populations across Nigeria, which may be influenced by factors such as regional differences in malaria transmission intensity, healthcare infrastructure, and local drug resistance patterns. Although the specific mutations identified in this study have not yet been linked to delayed parasite clearance or artemisinin resistance, they could potentially contribute to these phenomena in the future, especially if selective pressure from widespread ACT usage continues to drive genetic evolution in *P. falciparum*.

The presence of both synonymous and non-synonymous mutations in the *PfK13* gene in the Anambra State population indicates a level of genetic diversity in *P. falciparum* strains. This diversity is crucial for understanding how *P. falciparum* may evolve in response to drug pressure. Synonymous mutations, while not altering the amino acid sequence of the protein, can still have significant effects on the stability and efficiency of mRNA and protein production. These mutations may influence how the parasite responds to the host environment, which can affect its ability to survive and proliferate. Conversely, non-synonymous mutations, which alter the protein's structure, could have more immediate consequences for the parasite's ability to resist treatment, as changes in protein function are more likely to directly impact the efficacy of drugs like artemisinin.

The observed mutations in this study, particularly the non-synonymous mutations A577S and V638D, lead to no changes in the *PfK13* protein's folding, stability, or function, which have no effect on the parasite's response to ACTs. For instance, the A577S mutation results in the substitution of alanine (a small, nonpolar amino acid) with serine (a polar amino acid), which could affect the protein's interaction with other molecules involved in the parasite's survival. Similarly, the V638D mutation, which involves the substitution of valine (a nonpolar amino acid) with aspartic acid (a negatively charged, polar amino acid), could disrupt hydrophobic interactions within the protein, potentially affecting its function and interaction with other cellular components. These structural changes do not alter the parasite's ability to clear drugs from its system or develop mechanisms to withstand treatment.

The current findings are in line with previous research conducted in other regions of Nigeria, such as a study in Southwestern Nigeria by Ikegbunam [5] although not much differences in the specific mutations identified. This variability highlights the need for region-specific surveillance and monitoring programs to track the evolution of *PfK13* mutations and their potential impact on malaria treatment. Additionally, the findings are not consistent with studies in other African countries, such as Rwanda, where a gradual increase in the frequency of *PfK13* mutations was observed over a period of years, suggesting that resistance may develop slowly but steadily over time. The study conducted in Rwanda also found evidence of non-synonymous mutations, such as P574L and A675V, in later years (2014 and 2015), suggesting a gradual accumulation of mutations in response to ACT pressure. Similar patterns may emerge in Nigeria, underscoring the importance of continued monitoring and the need for molecular surveillance to detect emerging resistance mutations early.

5. Conclusion

The results of this study underscore the presence of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within the *PfK13* gene in the samples analyzed from COOUTH. While the study did not identify mutations directly associated with delayed parasite clearance or artemisinin resistance, it is significant that two non-synonymous and three synonymous mutations were detected. The non-synonymous mutations, specifically A577S and V638D, may have potential implications for protein structure and function, potentially affecting the parasite's response to antimalarial treatment. However, these mutations have yet to be conclusively linked to delayed parasite clearance or artemisinin resistance in the study region. The absence of well-established resistance mutations like C580Y, R539T, Y493H, and M476I further suggests that while genetic mutation in *P. falciparum* exists in Anambra State, it may not yet be associated with the same resistance observed in other malaria-endemic regions, such as Southeast Asia.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study orally.

References

- [1] Aka KG, Traoré DF, Sagna AB, Zoh DD, Assi SB, Tchikoi BN, Adja AM, Remoue F, Poinsignon A.(2020). Pattern of antibody responses to Plasmodium falciparum antigens in individuals differentially exposed to Anopheles bites. *Malar J*.;19(1):83. doi: 10.1186/s12936-020-03160-5. PMID: 32085710; PMCID: PMC7033907.
- [2] Arieu F, Witkowski B, Amaratunga C, Beghain J, Langlois AC, Khim N, Kim S, Duru V, Bouchier C, Ma L, Lim P, Leang R, Duong S, Sreng S, Suon S, Chuor CM, Bout DM, Ménard S, Rogers WO, Genton B, Fandeur T, Miotto O, Ringwald P, Le Bras J, Berry A, Barale JC, Fairhurst RM, Benoit-Vical F, Mercereau-Puijalon O, Ménard D.(2014). A molecular marker of artemisinin-resistant Plasmodium falciparum malaria. *Nature*.;505(7481):50-5. doi: 10.1038/nature12876. Epub 2013 Dec 18. PMID: 24352242; PMCID: PMC5007947.
- [3] Burrows T, Goldman S, Pursey K, Lim R.(2017). Is there an association between dietary intake and academic achievement: a systematic review. *J Hum Nutr Diet*. 117-140. doi: 10.1111/jhn.12407. Epub 2016 Sep 7. PMID: 27599886.
- [4] Çelik, A., Yaman, H., Turan, S., Kara, A., Kara, F., Zhu, B., Qu, X., Tao, Y., Zhu, Z., Dhokia, V., Nassehi, A., Newman, S. T., Zheng, L., Neville, A., Gledhill, A., Johnston, D., Zhang, H., Xu, J. J., Wang, G., ... Dutta, D. (2018). A Review of Waste Management Techniques in parts of Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 1(1), 1–8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2016.06.001>
- [5] Ikegbunam, M., Krueger, T., Lissom, A., Sandri, T. L., Ntahi, J. D. M., Djontu, J. C., Baina, M. T., Lontchi, R. A. L., Maloum, M., Ella, G. Z., Agonhossou, R., Akoton, R., Djogbenou, L., Borrmann, S., Held, J., Ntoumi, F., Adegnika, A. A., Kremsner, P. G., & Kreidenweiss, A. (2023). Low Prevalence of Plasmodium falciparum Histidine-Rich Protein 2 and 3 Gene Deletions—A Multiregional Study in Central and West Africa. *Pathogens*, 12(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12030455>
- [6] Khodzhaeva, N. M., Baranova, A. M., & Tokmalaev, A. K. (2019). The immunological plasmodium falciparum malaria characteristics of children in Tajikistan Republic. In *Journal of Tropical Medicine* (Vol. 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5147252>
- [7] Mayengue PI, Niama RF, Kouhounina Batsimba D, Malonga-Massanga A, Louzolo I, Loukabou Bongolo NC, Macosso L, Ibara Ottia R, Kimbassa Ngoma G, Dossou-Yovo LR, Pembet Singana B, Ahombo G, Sekangue Obili G, Kobawila SC, Parra HJ.(2018). No polymorphisms in K13-propeller gene associated with artemisinin resistance in Plasmodium falciparum isolated from Brazzaville, Republic of Congo. *BMC Infect Dis*.;538. doi: 10.1186/s12879-018-3453-6. PMID: 30373565; PMCID: PMC6206645.
- [8] Mokuolu, O. A., Ntadom, G. N., Ajumobi, O. O., Alero, R. A., Wammanda, R. D., Adedoyin, O. T., Okafor, H. U., Alabi, A. D., Odey, F. A., Agomo, C. O., Edozieh, K. U., Fagbemi, T. O., Njidda, A. M., Babatunde, S., Agbo, E. C., Nwaneri, N. B., Shekarau, E. D., Obasa, T. O., & Ezeigwe, N. M. (2016). Status of the use and compliance with malaria rapid diagnostic tests in formal private health facilities in Nigeria. *Malaria Journal*, 15(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-015-1064-x>
- [9] Munier FL, Beck-Popovic M, Chantada GL, Cobrinik D, Kivelä TT, Lohmann D, Maeder P, Moll AC, Carcaboso AM, Moulin A, Schaiquevich P, Bergin C, Dyson PJ, Houghton S, Puccinelli F, Vial Y, Gaillard MC, Stathopoulos C. (2019). Conservative management of retinoblastoma: Challenging orthodoxy without compromising the state of metastatic grace. "Alive, with good vision and no comorbidity". *Prog Retin Eye Res*.;100764. doi: 10.1016/j.preteyeres.2019.05.005. Epub 2019 Jun 5. Erratum in: *Prog Retin Eye Res*. 2020 Apr 8:100857. doi: 10.1016/j.preteyeres.2020.100857. PMID: 31173880.

- [10] Muwanguzi, J., Henriques, G., Sawa, P., Bousema, T., Sutherland, C. J., & Beshir, K. B. (2016). Lack of K13 mutations in *Plasmodium falciparum* persisting after artemisinin combination therapy treatment of Kenyan children. In *Malaria Journal* (Vol. 15, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-016-1095-y>
- [11] Ocan M, Obuku EA, Bwanga F, Akena D, Richard S, Ogwal-Okeng J, Obua C.(2015). Household antimicrobial self-medication: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the burden, risk factors and outcomes in developing countries. *BMC Public Health*.;15:742. doi: 10.1186/s12889-015-2109-3. PMID: 26231758; PMCID: PMC4522083.
- [12] WHO. (2018). World Health Organization Malaria Burden Report.
- [13] Wirjanata, G., Marsh, K. C., Duffy, J., Noviyanti, R., Rochford, R., McPhail, J. A., Njoroge, M., Smith, D. A., Birkholtz, L.-M., Reader, J., Siegl, P., Mancama, D., Wittlin, S., Donini, C., Herreros, E., Fish, P. V., de Kock, C., Lawrence, N., Waterson, D., ... Basarab, G. S. (2018). Erratum for Brunshwig et al., "UCT943, a Next-Generation *Plasmodium falciparum* PI4K Inhibitor Preclinical Candidate for the Treatment of Malaria" . *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 62(9), 1–16.
- [14] Woodrow, C. J., & White, N. J. (2017). The clinical impact of artemisinin resistance in Southeast Asia and the potential for future spread. In *FEMS Microbiology Reviews* (Vol. 41, Issue 1, pp. 34–48). <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsre/fuw037>
- [15] World Health Organization. (2023). Regional data and trends briefing kit World malaria. *World Malaria Report 2023*, December, 1–16.